

Deliverable 2.2

Network of the Hubs of success

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WP2 Task Force

Co-funded by
the Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Project Acronym	UNITA
Project Title	UNITA - Universitas Montium
Document Author	WP2 UNITA Teaching and learning: flexible and student-centred
Project Coordinator	Maurizio De Tullio
Project Duration	36 months
Deliverable No.	2.2 Network of the Hubs of success
Dissemination level *	PU
Work Package	WP2
Task	2.1.2
Lead beneficiary	Université Savoie Mont Blanc
Due date of deliverable	31/10/2021
Actual submission date	30/10/2021
Document version	1.0

* PU = Public; PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services); RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services); CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Agency Services)

Abstract

This document outlines the implementation of the Unita Hub of Success (HoS).

The HoS refers to a group of administrative and academic staff devoted to support and to counsel students on Unita mobility experiences.

A spreadsheet gathering all the informations is available on the Datacloud WP2 folder.

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1. Framework

The application for the constitution of the UNITA - Universitas Montium alliance foresaw, from the outset, a set of tasks to be carried out by Work Package 2, in relation to Supporting the personalisation and recognition of study paths, as follows:

In order to support students in the definition of tailored curricula (Personal and Professional Plan, PPP), UNITA sets up “Hubs of Success”. Hubs of Success are two-fold: as digital spaces on the Inter-campus platform they offer lists of contact persons (professors in charge of the mobility programmes with the UNITA universities in the Departments involved), who can advise them on how to plan their mobility in the host UNITA university based on the matrix of recognizable activities; as physical spaces they are located at the UNITA office and offer educational and vocational counselling services, learning support and individual monitoring of students participating in physical mobility.

HoS are the first landing site for UNITA students during their mobility and offer both onsite and remote (livechat) counselling. They also support disabled students when moving and students with learning disabilities, sharing best practices on inclusion at the UNITA universities.

The matrix and the HoS are discussed with the Student Assembly which is in charge of sharing the information with the student at the UNITA universities.

UNITA HoS cooperate through smart communication tools with the Education offices at the different UNITA universities in order to assess the feasibility of the Personal and Professional Plan

Ind.2.1.a Number of students consulting the Hubs of Success: 3000

Thus, following the scope of the established tasks, the following strategic plan is drawn up:

1. In order to reach the number of consultation, the scenario of consultation should be as much as possible close to the processes related to regular internationalization

consultation. Therefore the persons composing the Unita HoS should be identified among the staff in relation with students mobility counselling.

2. As within Unita, new activities and new opportunities for internationalizing, in a tailored way, the students' study paths, specific tools are created in order to promote these new possibilities. Unita HoSs have to be trained in using these specific tools.

Thus, the following strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats can be identified:

Strengths:

- Existing strong one-to-one collaborations
- Experienced international relation offices in each university
- UNITA offices in each university
- Work Packages dedicated to mobility : WP2 devoted to the reinforcement of the internationalization framework, WP6 devoted to new international activities

Weaknesses:

- HEIs of very different size (from 7.000 students to 85.000)
- Rigid study programs within all institution
- Academic calendars are different, unfavorizing short mobilities

Opportunities:

- Attract prospective students to UNITA universities
- Making UNITA a benchmarking object
- Enhance mobilities
- Development of international skills
- Contribution to internationalization of study programs

Threats:

- Lack of involvement from administrative staff and pedagogical referents

2. Unita Hub of Success - HoS

2.1 General

In its first-year version, UNITA HoS's missions are:

1. Promoting all kind of mobility within Unita
2. Identifying tailored and flexible study paths for long term mobility
3. Supporting the recognition of transversal skills associated to an international mobility

These 3 main missions correspond to the 3 type of consultations that a students can do. The HoS can be consulted at any period of the academic year. However, the period of preparation the long term mobility (from January to March) corresponds to a favorable period.

At the current stage, incoming students are in relation with the HoS through regular “welcome events” organized by IRO. They may consult host institution's HoS for being informed and involved of possible Unita's activities during their mobility.

The 3 type of consultations are described hereafter:

1. All students preparing a long term mobility, or even interested in a short mobility (physical, blended or virtual), can consult in a face-to-face way, or digitally, a HoS. The HoS presents all Unita's activities that are relevant depending on the request and the practical possibilities of the student. In the preparation of a long-term mobility, the period of consultation is focused mainly from January to April. For short mobilities, the consultation can be done all along the academic year.

The HoS presents the process associated to each activity, and how the recognition of the activity may be taken into account for the obtention of a degree.

The student will have the possibility to access to the set of these offers through a virtual gate. The virtual gate should be located in the Unita virtual campus. By this way, the counting of number of consultation can be done in an automatic process.

2. The second type of consultation concerns only students involved in a study program related to one of the 3 strategic areas: circular economy, renewable energy and cultural heritage. The HoS proposes recognized study paths within Unita study programs. The study paths are

tailored with respect to the student individual project. They also include at least a long term mobility period within Unita. In order to produce such proposals, the HoS use an ergonomic and user-friendly cartography (T5.2.2) allowing a user-friendly visualization of the all the subjects and the degrees related to the 3 strategic areas (T2.1.1). This type of consultation aims to promote the internationalization of curricula.

3. The third type of consultation is related to the support for the identification and the acquisition of transversal skills related to an international mobility experience. When a student is preparing a long term mobility, he is invited to participate to an activity consisting in assessing basic skills that he will get along his study abroad. These basic skills, at the current version, are the 5 following ones:

- Communication
- Intercultural sensitivity
- Adapting
- Team work and collaboration
- Learning

Whenever the student agrees in identifying and putting a practical content into these transversal skills, he is supported by an expert HoS member all along the activity. It starts before the mobility with an interview and a questionnaire. During the mobility experience, the student must put himself in relevant situations, yielding an increase of skills' level. He has to relate and provide tangible elements into a document. When the student comes back to his home institution, the expert HoS member verifies the consistency of the proofs put in the student's document. At this stage, a recognition of the acquired skills is formalized through a certificate. It is also integrated into a Unita diploma supplement (T6.3.2) and to the student's europass (T6.3.3).

For this activity, the HoS's accompaniment may be done during the whole academic year, but with an off-peak period of several months before the student physical mobility.

2.2 Organization of HoS

The HoS is composed by staff members from existing offices or department. Their physical location is thus identified. In addition, a virtual gate will be implemented in order to complete the accessibility to the counselling. This virtual place is not ready

at the current moment. We expect the virtual communication service to be implemented during the year 2022.

At the Unita level, between each HoS, the members communicate through their Unita Office, that is a part of the HoS. On one hand, the Unita Office is locally connected with both international relation offices and education offices ; on the other hand, the Unita Offices communicate in very fluid and reactive manner since the beginning of the Unita project.

In terms of type of consultation, the HoS activities are presented as follows:

Table 1: Unita HoS activities

	Missions	Objectives	Tools	Concerned students	Estimated target
Consultation I	Promoting all kind of mobility within Unita	Enhancing Unita mobility of all kind: short and long-term, physical, blended, and virtual	Digital booklet of Unita's activities	All students	Total of 2000
Consultation II	Identifying tailored and flexible study paths for long term mobility	Enhancing Unita learning agreements	Cartography of Unita study path	Bachelor and Master students concerned by a long term mobility and involved in a study program related to one of the 3 strategic areas (circular economy, cultural heritage and renewable energy).	Total of 800
Consultation III	Supporting the recognition of transversal skills associated to	Delivering a formal recognition of transversal skills related to an	Unita Personal and Professional Plan activity	All students concerned with a physical mobility	Total of 200

	Missions	Objectives	Tools	Concerned students	Estimated target
	an international mobility	international mobility			

2.3 Tools

HoS tools must be related to an up-to-date offer of possibilities designed by all the universities of the alliance.

2.3.1 Digital booklet of Unita's activities

- The digital booklet of Unita's activities corresponds to a comprehensive and attractive presentation of all the pedagogical activities implemented through all the Unita's actions. One of the aim is to present at a glance the advantages associated to a Unita mobility. At the current stage, the pedagogical activities linked to a mobility, are mainly related to:

- the catalog of virtual courses (T6.1.3)
- the rural mobilities (T6.2.1)
- intercomprehension training (T3.2.2)

In addition to these activities, in the framework of long-term mobilities, a Unita student has the opportunity to choose freely courses among the host university offer, up to 20% (6 ECTS/semester) of his learning agreement (T6.1.2).

Along the academic year 2021-2022, the offer of Unita's activities will be enriched with:

- blended intensive programs related to: intercomprehension (T3.2.3), research-based training at Master level (T4.2.2)
- microcredentials in: intercomprehension (T3.2.3), introduction to research at the Bachelor level (T.4.2.1), a European identity course (T7.3.1)

A consultable version by the students is proposed in the Unita websites of all institutions of the alliance.

2.3.2 Cartography

From T2.1.1, online Matrix, with T5.2.1, and T5.2.2, the interactive cartography is implemented in order to facilitate the construction of tailored and flexible study paths. These study paths are used for establishing students learning agreements.

For details, see the related deliverable D.2.1.1, D5.2.1 and D5.2.2.

2.3.3 IPPP activity

The iPPP activity aims to formalize and to recognize transversal skills associated to an international mobility. It takes inspiration from the Erasmus+ project “European Cross-Border Skills”, in which 3 universities of Unita have been involved (UNIZAR, UPPA and USMB).

Table 2: Unita HoS tools

	Main users	Students version	Location	Contributors	Updating
Digital booklet of Unita's activities	IRO + UO	yes	Unita's web site + virtual campus (later)	All Unita WP Task Force	By WP2 and UOs
Cartography of Unita study path	IRO+pedagogical referent	Yes	Provisional webserver, later on Virtual campus	WP2+IT+educational office	WP2 and IT
Unita Personal and Professional Plan activity	Pedagogical engineer+teacher involved in students mobility Table 2: Unita HoS tools	By construction	Provisional webserver, later on Virtual campus	WP2+pedagogical engineers	WP2+pedagogical engineers

An upgrade of the missions and the tools associated to HoS is expected during the year 2022, taking into account new Unita's activities, a consolidation of former ones and an enlargement of the missions (vocational counseling, student-life accompaniment)

2.4 Specific skills and knowledge associated of HoS

The project outlined for the UNITA alliance cover a wide range of services.

However, in its 1rst-year version, the HoS will focus only on the services associated to mobility experience.

Unita HoS is composed within each institution following a similar model:

1. IRO staff members;
2. Teachers, involved in IR;
3. Pedagogical engineers;
4. Unita Office members;

The related skills and knowledges are:

- International mobility counselling
- Internal student mobility process
- Level requirements related to a mobility
- Unita students' activities
- Home study programs
- Associated skills (prerequisites and expected outcomes)
- skills assessment
- Conceptual skill framework
- Skill-based approach activity

A later upgrade of the missions of HoS will include tasks related to the professional insertion and the student life.

3. Unita HoS contacts

Below the list of the identified HoS members, and their main role

Table 3: UNITA HoS contacts, per institution

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT
Unita Office - mobility	internacional@ubi.pt	unitacontact@unizar.es	unita-mobilites@univ-pau.fr	mobilitate-unita@univ-smb.fr	unita@unito.it	international@e-uvt.ro
International Relation Office	See the spreadsheet on Datacloud					
Pedagogical engineers			Mathilde.cames@univ-pau.fr	In recruitment process		

Table 4: Office/service related to study monitoring

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT
Study monitoring						
In charge of individual student's follow-up	GAP - Psychological Support Office/Internationalization (GI) for mobility students/Academic services (international students)	X	study programmes coordinators (years managers) and SCUIO-IP and DRI	scolarités pédagogiques / SCUIOP	Students/administrative education office (Edumeter teaching assessment)	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Student Information Center Student Schooling Management Center At faculty level: - vicedean responsible for students affairs, - responsible/coordinator of the study program, - tutors - professors who carry out activities within the study program
Involved in the reflexion of pedagogical councils	Course Scientific Committee / Pedagogical Council	X	DEVE and Conseil de perfectionnement and ODE and ARTICE and SUP and Collèges	CFVU	Teachers/QA commission/administrative education office/stakeholders	Center of Academic Development (CDA)
Coordination of students' pedagogical tutoring and	Internationalization Office (GI) in association with the Mobility Coordinator. For student ambassadors,	X	pedagogical tutoring : DEVE and Cellule Handicap. ESN		Buddy project/OTP services/teachers/student disability office	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Peer to Peer

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT
student ambassadors	association with ESN Covilhã					Tutoring Program (P2PT)
Internationalization of study path	Internationalization Office (GI)	X	Mobility coordinator of the formation and DRI	SFIO/international Office/SCUIOP	Teachers/International Services/administrative education office/linguistic center (CLA)	Quality Management Department (DMC) Department of International Relations (DRI)
Personalization of study path	Internationalization Office (GI) in association with the Mobility Coordinator	X	Mobility coordinator of the formation and DRI and SCUIO-IP	SFIO/SCUIOP	Teachers/administrative education office	Quality Management Department (DMC) Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC)
Long life learners accompaniment	People enter through the "over 23" contest but have to follow the normal route / Accreditation committee	X	FOR.CO	SUFCEP	CLA (Linguistic Center)/Teachers/administrative education office (pstlaurea programme)	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Department of Lifelong Learning, Distance Learning and Reduced Frequency (DECIDFR)
Professional insertion						
Inform on professional opportunities	Professional Exits, Employability and ALUMNI Office	X	SCUIO-IP and BAIP and UPPA CAREER CENTER and study programmes	GUIDE / BAIP	Job Quality Management Department (DMC) Department of International Relations (DRI) Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Placement/Administrative office (ILO, C-	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Department Responsible of the Relationship with Employers and Alumni (DRMSEA) Faculties

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT
					lab)/teachers(AlmaLaurea (future?))	
Gather and make available internship and job offers in the region and abroad	Professional Exits, Employability and ALUMNI Office	X	SCUIO-IP and BAIP and UPPA CAREER CENTER	GUIDE / Bureau des stages UFR	Job Placement	Department Responsible of the Relationship with Employers and Alumni (DRMSEA)
Organize events on professions and student-company networking	Professional Exits, Employability and ALUMNI Office	X	SCUIO-IP and BAIP and study programmes	BAIP	Companies/ Job Placement/teachers	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Department Responsible of the Relationship with Employers and Alumni (DRMSEA) Entrepreneurial Students Society (SAS) Faculties
Organize workshops on job search methodology	Professional Exits, Employability and ALUMNI Office / núcleos de estudiantes	X	SCUIO-IP and BAIP	BAIP	Job Placement Quality Management Department (DMC) Department of International Relations (DRI) Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC)	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC)
Guide students in their search strategy for internships or jobs	Professional Exits, Employability and ALUMNI Office		SCUIO-IP and BAIP and study programmes	BAIP	Teachers/ Job Placement	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC)

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT
Student life						
Coordinate all actions related to student life and their promotion : health and wellness-being, accommodation, food, transportation, culture, sports	SASUBI - Social Action Services/GAP - Psychological Support Office	X	SUMPPS and CROUS and Service culturel (MDE) and SUAPS ans CLOUS	GUIDE / SVEC	Students/common academic services/Edisu (Regional scholarships and accomodationQuality Management Department (DMC) Department of International Relations (DRI) Counseling and Career GuidanceQuality Management Department (DMC) Department of International Relations (DRI) Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Center (CCOC) service)/CUS (University Sport Center)	Quality Management Department (DMC) Social Service Vice-rector responsible for the academic strategy and student' affairs
integration of students in a situation of disability	SASUBI - Social Action Services/GAP - Psychological Support Office	X	Cellule Handicap	CELLULE HANDICAP	administrative educationQuality Management Department (DMC) Department of International Relations (DRI) Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) office/co-housing project	Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC) Center for Psycho-Pedagogical Assistance and Integration (CAIP)
relations with student associations	UBI Academic Association / We also have several cultural and student groups	X	ESN and MDE	SVEC	Students/administrative office	Quality Management Department (DMC)
welcoming incoming mobility students	Internationalization Office (GI)	X	Welcome Desk and DRI	DRI + relais RI UFR	Teachers/Buddy/international services	Quality Management Department (DMC) Department of

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT
						International Relations (DRI) Counseling and Career Guidance Center (CCOC)

4. Further development

As a perspective, HoS is aimed to enlarge its activity to vocational counselling. This will be achieved with the implication of the local associated partners.

The monitoring of communication skill, in an international contexte, could integrate the specificities of the intercomprehension approach, as the later is developed within all institutions of the alliance.

As a minor upgrade, more relevant names have been proposed:

- “International Mobility Advisory Team for Unita”, instead of “Hub of Success”
- “International Personal Carrer Plan”, instead of “Personal and Professional Plan”

The identification of existing offices within each institution, related to further missions that can be integrated to HoS’s ones. See Table 4.

5. Budget

The previsional budget for the UNITA HoS, totalling 184.000 €, is composed of:

- *Human Resources: 180.000 € for the recrutement during 2 years of a pedagogical engineer and a pedagogical counselor*
- *Events: around 4.000 € for the staff week for training involved staff members to the Unita’s tools.*

As the recrutement process is on working and the staff week is planned to happen in January 2022, expenditures have not yet taken place.

6.Evaluation of results

UNITA's HoS, as a service for students, must be assessed by them. Also, as the HoS is composed by both administrative and academic staffs, a self-assessment should be realized.

The measurement of the feedback results that will serve to adjust and redefine the organization, the missions and the processes associated to HoS.

Finally, it will be important to assess the HoS on an annual basis, with a half-yearly mid-term review, in order to ensure the updating of the informations that are intended to be shared and in line with the pursuit of continuous improvement of procedures.

7. Related documents

Related Documents	Location
UNITA HoS	Datacloud\3_U_WP2\deliverables